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THE USAGE OF HOMONYMS IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Annotation. There are terms in the Uzbek and English lexicon systems that are pronounced the same but have different meanings - homonyms, each of which has its unique linguistic features. This article covers homonyms, which are words that are phonologically and grammatically compatible but have distinct meanings. It also analyzes the properties of the English and Uzbek languages.

Annotatsiya. O‘zbek va ingliz tillari leksika tizimida talaffuzi bir xil bo‘lsa-da, ma’nosi turlicha bo‘lgan atamalar – omonimlar mavjud bo‘lib, ularning har biri o‘ziga xos til xususiyatlariga ega. Ushbu maqola fonologik va grammatik jihatdan mos keladigan, ammo alohida ma'noga ega bo'lgan omonimlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Shuningdek, omonimlarning ingliz va o‘zbek tillaridagi xususiyatlari tahlil qiladi.

Аннотация. В узбекской и английской лексических системах есть термины, которые произносятся одинаково, но имеют разное значение - омонимы, каждый из которых имеет свои уникальные языковые особенности. В этой статье рассматриваются омонимы, то есть слова, фонологические и грамматические совместимые, но имеющие разные значения. Также анализируются свойства английского и узбекского языков.

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In modern English language, the phenomenon of homonymy is widely developed. This phenomenon attracts many linguists to study its problems and attempt to classify homonyms in the English language. But, despite the fact that the study of homonymy has been conducted for a long time, there is still neither generally accepted definition of homonyms, nor established terminology in this area. The study of homonymy is especially important for understanding a foreign language, since in it different grammatical forms may have the same sound or spelling. In Russian language, this is usually not paid attention. Also, the knowing of homonyms is simply necessary in the practice of the English language, in which their number is much higher than in the Russian language. Homonymy presents itself a certain hindrance in the process of communication, when it is necessary to determine what exactly the meaning of the word corresponds to the context of speech. Also, words-homonyms are a problem for the speaker, who is forced to choose words in order to unambiguously understand his statements. The study of homonyms is extremely interesting in terms of tracking the historical meaning of the word and its changes in the process of language development. Modern English is characterized by a fairly significant number of homonyms, compared to other languages. In different languages, homonyms are always specific and no analogy

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between homonymous groups due to their random nature does not happen and cannot be. An important place in the linguistic description of homonyms is occupied by the problem of their classification.

The complete lexical homonymy is the coincidence of words belonging to one part of speech in all forms. An example of complete homonyms is the words “kul”-ashes, “kul”-smile; they do not differ in pronunciation and spelling, coincide in all case forms of the singular and plural. In the case of incomplete (partial) lexical homonymy, the coincidence in sound and spelling is observed in words belonging to one part of speech, but not in all grammatical forms. You can better understand the meaning of homonyms if you look at the origin of this linguistic term. In Uzbek there are a large number of various puzzles. Even those who speak Uzbek all their lives make a huge amount of mistakes when communicating: in using certain words, in accenting or in building sentences. Often confusion arises from the fact that two different words are spelled exactly the same. To a foreigner who is just starting to learn Uzbek, these words can cause a lot of problems.

After all, their meaning can be understood only by tracing the context. But this is not the only secret concealed by homonyms. The greatest difficulty arises when you try to explain to a foreigner how the homonyms and polysemantic words differ. If you do not go deeper into the definition, then polysemantic words are also written the same, but have different meanings.

Methods and Materials

Different forms of lexical homonymy are known, as well as phenomena related to it at other levels of language (phonetic and morphological). Complete lexical

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homonymy is the matching of words belonging to a part of speech in all other forms. Examples of complete homonyms are Uzbek "olma" - apple fruit and "olma" - not to receive, the verb to act; they do not differ in pronunciation and spelling, they are compatible in all conventional forms of singular and plural. With incomplete (partial) lexical homonymy, it is observed that words belonging to a part of speech correspond to sound and writing. However, this is not the case in all grammatical forms. For example, incomplete homonyms: Uzbek "o't" - grass, split plant and "o't" - fire. The second quoted word does not have a plural form, but it does exist in the first. The homonymous verbs Uzbek "tomchilamoq" (water, rain) and "tomchilamoq" (medicine) have the same indefinite forms (drip); adjectives of the present and past tense (tomchilash). But in exact ratio forms they do not match. According to their structure, homonyms can be divided into root and artificial. The roof has a base that cannot be made for homonyms: in Uzbek "tom" is the "roof of the building" and "tom" is "to drip". The second is based on the word formation and has a basis: Uzbek "qoplama" - "covering" and "qoplama" - "don't cover". Along with homonymy, there are related phenomena, ie features related to grammatical, phonetic and graphic language levels.

1. Depending on the similarity of pronunciation, homofoms, ie words that correspond in some grammatical form, are distinguished. For example, Uzbek "qoralama" - "draft", "do not paint the surface black" is a command to the 2nd person, and "qoralama" - a noun meaning "a sketch". The grammatical form of the words of a part of speech can also be homonymous. For example, the Uzbek word "yosh", which is a form of adjective, can mean youth and longevity. Such forms

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are adapted to the owner and vary in different arrangements. Homoforms, by their nature, go beyond the 10634 Journal of Positive School Psychology © 2022 JPPW. All rights reserved scope of lexicon because they belong to a different level of language and they need to study morphology.

2. Some languages have words that are pronounced the same but spelled differently.

They are called homophones. The word is derived from Greek and means homos - same + phone - sound. For example, in Uzbek, words such as "sol" and "so'l", "gul" and "go'l" are similar in pronunciation, and consonant sounds are not noticeable at the end of the word. A change in vowels can also cause the word to sound similar in pronunciation. Consequently, homophones are phonetic homonyms, and their formation in language is related to the movement of phonetic laws. Homophony can also manifest in a broad case. For example, several words may sound similar to each other depending on how they sound. This phenomenon is observed in the rubai of the famous Uzbek medieval poets - Navoi and Babur. Homophony is studied not by the field of lexicology, but by the science of phonetics, because it is manifested at the level of another language - the phonetic level.

3. There are also words that are spelled the same but pronounced differently, and are called homographs. The word homograph means in Greek homos - same + grapho - I write. Usually they differ in the application of stress in different joints. Omography has a direct connection to the graphical system of language. Strict differentiation of linguistic phenomena requires the delimitation and separation of

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original lexical homonyms from homoforms, homophones, and homographs.

Discussion

Homonyms in English are usually divided into 5 groups: Absolute homonyms or pairs of words with identical sound and spelling. The difference is only in meaning, transcription and spelling are completely the same. Example: band [bænd] is a bandage and band [bænd] is a band. Homophones (heteronyms) or words with the same sound but different spelling. Example: be [bi:] - to be and bee [bi:] - a bee. Homographs. It's the opposite. Words are written the same way, but read differently. Example: bow [bau] - bow and bow [bəu] - bow. Neither here nor here, i.e., these are words with similar pronunciation and spelling. Example: lose [lu:z] - lose, loose [lu:s] - weaken. In capitonyms, the differences are in the spelling of the first letter (uppercase or lowercase). Example: Mercury ['mɜ:kjəri] - Mercury (planet) and mercury ['mɜ:kjəri] - mercury (chemical element). Let's move from theory to practice. For this, I will give some examples of English sentences with homonyms: -My mom must accept that my brother likes all vegetables except for turnips. "My mom should add that my brother loves all vegetables except turnips." -While baking a cake with flour, I received a flower from my boyfriend. - While I was interfering with a cake with flour, I received a flower from my boyfriend. -The mailman delivered two packages to me, too. "The postman also (= too) delivered two packages for me." -Ben left through the left door. - Ben left through the left door. -Your house is big enough to house your entire library of books. "Your house is big enough to house your entire library." -I scream. You scream. We all scream for icescream. - I'm screaming. You're yelling.

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We all scream about ice cream.

Conclusion: Based on the available analysis, the main factor determining the formation of homonyms in English is word formation. Another sign of it can serve to distinguish homonyms as well as to distinguish their meanings. In conclusion, it is very difficult to distinguish between homonymy and polysemy. Each concept and word has only one meaning, and that meaning is associated with a single character. However, if this ratio is in one language, it does not occur in another. When choosing a word, it is important to know its meaning and usage, as well as whether the word is compatible with other words.

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